

"THE EFFECTIVE LEARNING OF ENGLISH GRAMMAR ' TENSES' THROUGH MULTI MEDIA PACKAGE FOR THE STUDENTS OF STANDARD IX

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Paper Received On 20 June 2023

Peer Reviewed On 22 July 2023

Published On: 1 August 2023

Abstract

This study examined the effect of multimedia package teaching strategy on the students' achievement in English to Std IX. It also examined the differential effects in the achievement among Standard IX students. The study used two groups pretest-posttest equivalent-groups design, 50 students for adopting for the present research. English Tense Forms (ETF) Test developed by the researcher has been used for the present study. Students were taught using multimedia package strategy who achieved higher scores and significantly better than those taught using conventional (lecture) method. The study recommended among other things that since multimedia package is found to be an effective strategy and has an enhanced achievement among Standard IX students, the teachers of this subject may accept it as one of the strategies and they can use this for their English grammar teaching.

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INTRODUCTION

Education technology is relatively a new field which aims at solving problems of teaching and learning. Hardware and software are two structural components of this technology and multimedia is an important aspect of this technology. Education as a system, has some objectives that are planned for the realization of strategies, techniques and aids which must have been designed and devised by educational technologists.

We live in a world of Media. We have a visual culture, living in an environment influenced by media messages of every kind. In recent years, we have also seen media, assume an increasingly important role in every aspect of instructional planning and designing. Learning is a steady and gradual process. Its pace, however, can be accelerated by involving maximum number of senses. Research studies have also shown beyond doubt that through the selection and

use of appropriate new educational communication material and new education media, many of the obstacles to the creation of an environment for effective learning can be overcome by the use of educational media. Multimedia approach is one such innovation aimed at improving the teaching-learning process much easier, better and with more creativity.

Multimedia learning experiences represent a natural way for learning to take place. Learning pace can be accelerated by involving maximum number of senses. Sensory experiences form the foundation of intellectual activity within any formal school situation and hence learners differ in the effectiveness of their sense reception. Multimedia learning experiences have the advantage of appealing to the individual, the learners pace, interest and readiness.

Besides, cognition and conceptualization, it depends of a chain of events, which begin with the learners' perception of stimuli, be they auditory, visual tactile and of factory. It is important that these initial learning experiences be accurate, dependable or understandable. Unless the learner's initial sensory impressions are accurate, it will be impossible for them to have reliable conceptualization and understanding. With the existing numerous kinds of aids, carefully organized presentation and through a variety of media it should occupy the learners conscious attention to living stimuli.

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The native Tamil speaking students (from rural areas specifically) face many problems in communication with English and grammar - tense formation because of the syntactical variation between Tamil and English languages. So they are not able to learn English language in all its levels of second language acquisition. Further their parents' social background, educational background and economical status play a very important variable which has determined the capacity of learning English in the students. The primary problem in students, they do not have the background knowledge of English language because they are not the original native speakers of English. The English language has transferred from British people during the period of colonial administration of British. The Indian students still find it difficult in learning English with its Listening and speaking, reading and writing skills and with using proper grammar structure and not using proper grammar respectively. The teachers are teaching English in school by translating into their mother tongue (Tamil) for his/ her subject content. These are the primary reasons which are considered for the immediate remedial source where the

students can find it easy to understand English and its Grammar through the use of multimedia package.

The term grammar covers the proper use of words and word forms as well as the grammatical structure of phrases, clauses and sentences and the grammatical categories that are marked by English inflectional morphology that may include tense, person, number, gender, case and comparison. Tense is a category that includes mainly the aspect of time, to indicate when an occurrence takes place. Tense is the grammaticalisation of time reference, often using three basic categories of past, the present, and the future. In consideration of all together, formation of tense in English is more essential rather than speaking fluently in English. If anyone properly uses the tense forms, he/she makes the communication to happen in a meaningful way to others. The students must be trained and strengthened from the schooling itself to frame the sentences properly with the proper use of tense forms. Since this process may involve greater difficulty in the students' perception of understanding the content, the researcher had made it easy to give the learning experience to the students through multimedia package. The effectiveness of multimedia package make the pupils to learn English Grammar Tenses by its visual and aural presentations of teaching the content. Moreover multimedia package provides more physical attention to receive the concept with attentive stimuli which will create real improvement in formation of tense in English. In order to fulfill the objectives of the study the investigator has developed multimedia package for school students for learning English and formation of tense in English. Therefore the present study is considered need and significance one of the present context.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The language English has been considered and treated as the Global language in Indian schools and hence, efforts are given more to the teaching of English to the pupils in India. 'Framing of sentences' is more necessary both for speaking and writing English. Through that a pupil can make a listener to understand what he/ she wants to convey more precisely. This may continue till their graduation and for job opportunities too which will definitely make them to learn Tenses with proper understanding and applying into their daily usages in English. With the traditional method of chalk and teach method, the process of teaching and learning of Grammar Tenses may take more time and difficulty in proper perception of students. Hence, a tool in Multimedia has been designed to learn English Grammar Tenses and so the statement can

be "THE EFFECTIVE LEARNING OF ENGLISH GRAMMAR ' TENSES' THROUGH MULTI MEDIA PACKAGE FOR THE STUDENTS OF STANDARD IX"

3.4 OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF THE KEY TERMS

EFFECTIVENESS

According to oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary (1999), Effectiveness defines having the desired effect and producing the intended result. This study measures the effectiveness in terms of the achievement scores of the students using multimedia in teaching English Grammar.

Multimedia

Multimedia is the combination of text, graphic, sound, animation and video elements delivered by computer.

Teaching

“ Giving systematic information, instruction or training to a person” .

- *Oxford advanced learners dictionary*

Teaching as, an interactive process, primarily involving classroom talk which takes place between teacher and the pupil and occurs during certain definable activities” .

- *Edmud Amidson (1967)*

English Grammar

The rules in a language for changing the form of words and combining them in to sentences. The present study. That is, Tense Forms with 'yes' or ' no' type questions and answers.

Objectives

1. To find out the significant difference in the mean scores of the control group and the experimental group in the learning objective-wise pre-test.
2. To find out the significant difference in mean scores of the control group and the experimental group in the learning objective-wise post test.
3. To find out the significant difference between the control group and the experimental group in the gain ratio in Grammar ' Tenses' .

HYPOTHESES

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of control group and experimental group in the learning objective-wise pre-test .
2. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of the control group and the experimental group in the learning objective-wise post test.

3. There is no significant difference between the control group and the experimental group in the gain ratio in Grammar ' Tenses'.

Methodology

Experimental design is the blue print of the procedures that enable the researcher to test hypotheses by reaching vivid conclusions about relationships between independent and dependent variables. In this experimental research, the investigator has chosen the two groups pretest-posttest equivalent-groups design for her study.

The pretest-posttest equivalent groups design is

$$\begin{array}{l} R \ O_1 \ X \ O_2 \quad X \text{ gain} = O_2 - O_1 \quad O_1 \ O_3 - \text{Pre tests} \\ R \ O_3 \ C \ O_4 \quad C \text{ gain} = O_4 - O_3 \quad O_2 \ O_4 - \text{Posttests} \end{array}$$

In this experimental method two groups of subjects are selected. One of the equivalent groups serves as the control group in which the subjects are taught by traditional method. The other group serves as the experimental group in which the subjects are taught using Concept Mapping Strategy. Both the groups had same number of students and they were given equal time for each session. The treatment was given for 20 days with a schedule of one hour per day for each group and no students were absent on those days. The treatment was given without any disturbances.

Tool Used

A research instrument which was validated by experts in English subject, measurement and evaluation was used for this study namely English tense form (ETF). The ETF was based on the difficult tense form concepts.

Sample

The sample for the present study constitutes 50 IX standard Students of Alpha Matric Higher Secondary School in Pondicherry. As per the scoring of a general test in English, 25 students were chosen as control group and 25 students were chosen as experimental group. Both groups were equated on the basis of their pretest scores (intelligence test)

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

Statistical techniques serve the fundamental purpose of description and inferential analysis. The following statistical techniques were used in the study.

- ❖ Mean (M) and standard deviations (SD)
- ❖ ‘t’ test for determining the significance of difference between the means of the two sub-groups.

ANNALYSIS OF DATA

Hypothesis: 1 There is no significant difference between the pre test and Post test learning objective-wise mean scores of the control group who were taught by the conventional teaching method.

TABLE 4.17 THE MEAN, SD AND ‘T’ VALUE OF CONTROL GROUP PRE AND POST TESTS IN TERMS OF LEARNING OBJECTIVE-WISE

Learning Objectives	Tests	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Sig.	
Lesson -1 K	Pre Test	25	8.16	1.17	2.51	Significant 0.05	P <
	Post Test	25	8.86	0.97			
Lesson -1 U	Pre Test	25	10.63	2.26	3.08	Significant 0.05	P <
	Post Test	25	11.23	2.01			
Lesson -1 A	Pre Test	25	9.11	2.19	3.55	Significant 0.05	P <
	Post Test	25	9.61	2.29			
Lesson -2 K	Pre Test	25	10.55	2.19	4.20	Significant 0.05	P <
	Post Test	25	12.61	2.23			
Lesson -2 U	Pre Test	25	11.10	2.75	4.87	Significant 0.05	P <
	Post Test	25	12.29	2.67			
Lesson -2 A	Pre Test	25	9.61	1.55	3.56	Significant 0.05	P <
	Post Test	25	8.61	1.25			
Lesson -3 K	Pre Test	25	10.44	1.50	8.94	Significant 0.05	P <
	Post Test	25	9.55	2.66			
Lesson -3 U	Pre Test	25	8.35	1.98	7.72	Significant 0.05	P <
	Post Test	25	9.26	2.08			
Lesson -3 A	Pre Test	25	9.76	1.69	4.96	Significant 0.05	P <
	Post Test	25	8.50	1.50			

From the table 4.9 it is observed that all the obtained ‘t’ values are more than the critical value at both level of significance (0.05 and 0.01 level) and hence, the null hypothesis that there was no significant difference between the pre and post test learning objective-wise mean scores of control group who were taught by conventional teaching method is rejected, and it was

interpreted here that the control group who underwent English Grammar in conventional teaching method gained more in the learning objective-wise post test than in the learning objective-wise pre test.

Hypothesis: 2 There is no significant difference between pre test and Post test learning objective-wise mean scores of experimental group who were taught by the Multi media learning package.

TABLE 4.19 THE MEAN, SD AND 'T' VALUE OF EXPERIMENTAL GROUP PRE AND POST TESTS IN TERMS OF LEARNING OBJECTIVE-WISE

Learning Objectives	Tests	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Sig.
Lesson -1 K	Pre Test	25	1.64	0.54	17.94	Significant P < 0.05
	Post Test	25	3.55	0.66		
Lesson -1 U	Pre Test	25	4.61	1.39	13.76	Significant P < 0.05
	Post Test	25	11.88	2.19		
Lesson -1 A	Pre Test	25	2.38	1.30	17.83	Significant P < 0.05
	Post Test	25	7.14	0.82		
Lesson -2 K	Pre Test	25	2.58	1.10	10.33	Significant P < 0.05
	Post Test	25	7.14	0.82		
Lesson -2 U	Pre Test	25	2.44	0.74	11.51	Significant P < 0.05
	Post Test	25	4.38	0.85		
Lesson -2 A	Pre Test	25	1.79	0.64	12.38	Significant P < 0.05
	Post Test	25	3.70	0.62		
Lesson -3 K	Pre Test	25	1.52	0.50	9.60	Significant P < 0.05
	Post Test	25	2.94	0.60		
Lesson -3 U	Pre Test	25	2.35	1.01	9.81	Significant P < 0.05
	Post Test	25	6.79	0.84		
Lesson -3 A	Pre Test	25	0.82	0.83	10.25	Significant P < 0.05
	Post Test	25	2.52	0.50		

From the table 4.12 it is observed that all the obtained 't' values are more than the critical value at both level of significance (0.05 and 0.01 level) and hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the pre and Post test learning objective-wise mean scores of experimental group who were taught by e-learning modules is rejected, hence it is interpreted here that the experimental group who were taught by blended learning modules performed more in the learning objective-wise post test than in the learning objective-wise pre test.

Hypothesis 3 : There is no significant difference between the control group and the experimental group in their gain ratio in English.

In order to test the above said null hypothesis the gain scores was calculated earlier in the following method. Guin and Peters (1965) suggested that best criterion of a programme effectiveness is the gain between the amount learned and the amount that could be learnt. So the following formula helped the present investigator to arrive gain ratio scores of the IX standard English Students after the treatments.

Mean of (Post test Scores – Pre test Scores)

Gain Ratio = -----

Mean of (Maximum in the Post test Scores – Pre test Scores)

Since the gain ratio is 1.03 and it indicates that the teaching through the blended-learning modules is more effective method than the conventional method of teaching of English to IX standard S

English Students. However the ‘t’ test was computed between the gain ratio scores of control group and experimental group.

TABLE 4.24 THE MEAN, SD OF GAIN RATIO SCORES BETWEEN EXPERIMENTAL AND CONTROL GROUP

Variable	Group	N	Mean	SD	‘t’	P
Gain Ratio	Experimental	25	6.93	0.23	4.78	Significant P < 0.01
	Control	25	2.71	0.16		

From the table 4.17 it is further evident that there is significant difference between the experimental and control group in the Gain Ratio Scores since, the obtained ‘t’ value (4.78) is more than the critical value at both 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance at 48 df. It is decided that the difference between control group and experimental group in gain ratio is highly significant, hence, it was concluded that the teaching through blended learning modules have a positive effect on learning English among IXth standard English students.

FIGURE 4.10 THE MEAN, SD OF GAIN RATIO SCORES BETWEEN EXPERIMENTAL AND CONTROL GROUP

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Teaching through multimedia method can be applied in all schools.
- Chalk & Talk method of teaching English should be avoided and new instructional teachings using multimedia package can be introduced.
- In this electronics world multimedia is a boon to all educational institutions at all levels. This resource therefore has to be utilized fully for maximizing the learning processes.
- Multimedia package can be used to enhance both the theoretical and practical knowledge.
- Teachers and lecturers can be trained to produce multimedia package at various levels. In service training and orientation courses, it can be provided through multimedia.
- In the multimedia package, the content can be further simplified as it is split up into small frames.
- In the multimedia package, the content may be presented in a more structural and systematic way.
- Without any prior exposure to the computer, computer software or any other educational software, any pupil can reap the benefits of multimedia package. So more packages may be developed.

CONCLUSION

This study clearly indicates that the multimedia package developed in teaching English Grammar for STD IX students was effective. The effectiveness was found in terms of posttest of the students of experimental group taught through multimedia. Multimedia no doubt is a new information technology product and also is a new thrust area for the professionals to develop user friendly multimedia system. Computer is the primary tool used in the multimedia system. Multimedia has changed the way of information gathering, repackaging and distributing to fellow professionals with its sound and visual capabilities. The technologists are trying to overcome the problems and are working progressively for different applications. Certainly multimedia will occupy a prominent place in the information centre as a modern tool in the 21st Century.

The new technology will pave the way to new opportunities and a paradigm shift. Multimedia will play a vital role in the educational field by developing self learning educational materials, computer aided instructional course materials, etc. The different author ware will help in developing, designing and production of multimedia information sources. It is the right time for the realization of new technology and the multimedia system.

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